

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF NEP 2020

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Abstract

The National Education Policy (NEP)2020 changes the traditional way of Education System. This education provides holistic, flexible and multidisciplinary framework suited to needs of 21st century. This system also increases the marks scoring ability of the students. Teachers also require to update their knowledge to adjust with changing requirement of education policy. Students are main beneficiary of any system of Education. They experience the positive and negative influence of NEP 2020 Education System. But recently state government introduced State Education policy. Hence it is essential to study the problems and opportunities of NEP2020. This Article mainly focus on problems and opportunities of NEP 2020. Primary data is collected from students, faculties and other interested groups. Suggestions and conclusion are drawn from primary data.

Key Words: *NEP2020. Multidisciplinary frame work. Students. Teachers. Problems and opportunities.*

Introduction

The National Education Policy 2020 is a comprehensive framework by the Indian government to transfer the countries education system. it replaced the previous 1986 policy with the goal of creating an equitable, Vibrant and knowledge-based society approach. It emphasizes a holistic and multi-disciplinary approach, integrating vocational skills and arts with academics, key aims of this education is include making education inclusive and accessible promoting foundational literacy, integrating technology and nurturing the creative potential of every individual.

Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential developing an equitable and just society and promoting national development. Providing universal access to quality

education is the key to India's continue ascent and leadership and the global stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality scientific advancement national integration and cultural preservation.

While the policy is ambitious and forward-looking, its successful implementation comes with challenges. An analysis of both the problems and prospects is essential to understand its real impact.

objectives

1. To analyse the prospects of NEP 2020 in terms of improving access, equity, quality, and employability.
2. To identify the major challenges and problems in the implementation of NEP 2020 across different levels of education.
3. To examine the impact of NEP 2020 on students, parents, and society.
4. To suggest measures and recommendations for overcoming barriers and achieving the intended goals of NEP 2020.

Methodology:

Qualitative and quantitative research is used to collect primary and secondary data.

Sources of Data:

Primary Data: Primary data is collected from structured questionnaire through google form from students, teachers, parents and other interested group of Tumkur city.

Secondary Data: This data is collected policy document, government reports, websites etc,

Limitations:

1. This data is collected from our college students, teachers, parents and other interested group of Tumkur only.
2. Time is the main limitation of this study.

Analysis of Data

2. Age:
56 responses

The data shows that the survey is youth-dominated, with over 92% of respondents below 30 years. This highlights that the opinions captured largely reflect the perspectives of students and young learners, who are the primary beneficiaries of NEP 2020.

3. Gender
56 responses

From the above chart gender distribution of the respondent, 52 respondent 92.9% are female and rest are male respondent.

4. Occupation

56 responses

Occupation of respondents” (56 responses):

Regarding occupation of the respondent is concerned, maximum respondent 48, 85.7% are students, this shows that the majority of perspectives are coming from learners, the primary beneficiaries of NEP 2020.

5. Educational qualification:

56 responses

Educational qualification of respondents” (56 responses):

This chart explains maximum 47 respondents 83.9% are undergraduate students, this survey primarily reflects the views of learners at the early stage of higher education.

6. Are you aware of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020?

56 responses

From the above, maximum respondents 96.4% are aware about the NEP 2020 System of Education. Only small 3.6% of respondents are not aware about NEP System of Education.

7. If yes, how would you rate our level of understanding of NEP?

56 responses

The results suggest that the overall awareness and understanding of NEP is high among respondents, with most rating it as good or very good. Only a small fraction feels their understanding is average, showing that stakeholders are generally well-informed about the policy.

8. In your opinion, what are the major challenges in implementing NEP?

56 responses

The main obstacles in implementing NEP are the digital divide, teacher readiness, and unlisted practical challenges, followed by funding, language, and resistance issues.

9. which of the following do you think are the strongest benefit of NEP?

56 responses

Majority respondents Value NEP mainly focus on employability and holistic education.

10. Do you agree, NEP can improve the quality of Education in India?

56 responses

Maximum respondents 55.4% agree and 32.1 % strongly agree the NEP improve the quality of Education in India.

11. Do you think NEP will help India to compete globally in higher education and Research?

56 responses

Majority of the respondent about 66.15 are strong belief that NEP will enhance Indian Global Competitiveness in higher education and research.

- 66.1% (37 respondents) answered “Yes”, indicating strong belief that NEP will enhance India’s global competitiveness in higher education and research.

12. what are the suggestions to improve the NEP -2020?

42 responses

Majority of the respondent suggest digitalization, reducing heavy syllabus and providing infrastructure facilities are essential for implement NEP system of education.

Findings:

1. Maximum female student respondents are covered under the survey.
2. Regarding educational background, undergraduate about 83.9% respondents are covered.
3. Maximum respondents that are 96.4% responses are aware about the national education policy.
4. Maximum respondents agreed that this NEP 2020 system of education is very good.
5. Major challenges of NEP 2020 education are lack of digital divide and teachers training.
6. This system of education improvises employability skills of students and also provide holistic and multi-disciplinary education.
7. NEP 2020 System of Education can improve the quality education system in India.
8. This system of education also enhances Indian global competitiveness in higher education and research.
9. Major challenges of this education are lack of digitalisation, lack of training to teachers, heavy syllabus and infrastructure facilities.
10. Flexibility system of education and this system of education enhance the skills of students.
11. Opportunities to learn different languages and different subjects.
12. Establishment of multidisciplinary universities and colleges.

13. Benefit of Academic Bank of Credits for flexible learning.

14 Focus on critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving.

Suggestions

1. Good infrastructure facilities are essential to effective adoption of New Education Policy 2020.
2. Teachers need extensive training to adapt to new pedagogy.
3. Reducing heavy syllabus is also main concept to improve the quality of education.
4. Ethical values are also important to overall development of youth education; hence it is required to adopt ethical values in education System.
5. Quality text books are also essential to enhance the knowledge students.
6. To adopt changing technology, changing mind set of students, parents and teachers are also require to improve NEP system of education.
7. Co-ordination among central and State government is also needed to improve NEP Education.
8. Financial support is also essential to colleges and universities for proper adoption of NEP system of Education.
9. Providing qualified educators in rural area is also essential to improve NEP Education.

Conclusion

NEP 2020 is a visionary document that has the potential to transform India's education system into one of the most progressive in the world. If implemented effectively, it will create a generation of learners equipped with skills, values, and knowledge to face global challenges. However, the success of NEP 2020 depends on overcoming financial, infrastructural, and pedagogical challenges. Strong political will, collaborative efforts between government and stakeholders, and continuous monitoring will be essential. If These problems are solved by Authorities, it is very much benefitted to both students and teachers.

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